

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 50

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 50

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 50:0 A Psalm of 'Asaph.</p>	<p>Psa. 50:1 מִזְמוֹר לְאַסָּף</p>
<p>Psa. 50:1 ^aThe Mighty One, God, the LORD, has spoken,</p>	<p>אֵל וְאֱלֹהִים יְהוָה דִּבֶּר</p>
<p>And summoned the earth ^bfrom the rising of the sun to its setting.</p>	<p>וַיִּקְרָא אֶרֶץ מִמִּזְרַח-שֶׁמֶשׁ עַד-מְבֹאוֹ : ² מִצִּיּוֹן מְכַלֵּל-</p>
<p>² Out of Zion, ^athe perfection of beauty,</p>	<p>יָפִי אֱלֹהִים הוֹפִיעַ : ³ יִבֹּא</p>
<p>God ^bhas shone forth.</p>	<p>אֱלֹהֵינוּ וְאֵל-יִתְרַשׁ אִישׁ-</p>
<p>³ May our God ^acome and not keep silence;</p>	<p>לְפָנָיו תֹּאכַל וְסִבִּיבָיו</p>
<p>^bFire devours before Him, And it is very ^ctempestuous</p>	<p>נִשְׁעָרָה מְאֹד : ⁴ יִקְרָא אֵל-</p>
<p>around Him.</p>	<p>הַשָּׁמַיִם מֵעַל וְאֵל-הָאָרֶץ</p>
<p>⁴ He ^asummons the heavens above,</p>	<p>לְדַיֵּן עַמּוֹ : ⁵ אֶסְפּוּ-לִי</p>
<p>And the earth, to judge His people:</p>	<p>תְּסִידֵי כָרְתִי בְרִיתִי עָלַי-</p>
<p>⁵ "Gather My ^agodly ones to Me, Those who have made a</p>	<p>זִבַּח : ⁶ וַיִּגִּידוּ שָׁמַיִם צְדָקוֹ</p>
<p>^bcovenant with Me by ^csacrifice."</p>	<p>כִּי-אֱלֹהִים אֲשַׁפֵּט הוּא</p>
<p>⁶ And the ^aheavens declare His righteousness,</p>	<p>סֵלָה : ⁷ שִׁמְעָה עַמִּי </p>
<p>For ^bGod Himself is judge.</p>	<p>וְאֵדְבָרָה יִשְׂרָאֵל וְאֶעֱיֶדָה</p>
<p>¹Selah.</p>	<p>בְּךָ אֱלֹהִים אֱלֹהֶיךָ אֲנֹכִי : ⁸</p>
<p>Psa. 50:7 ^aHear, O My people, and I will speak;</p>	<p>לֹא עַל-זִבְחֶיךָ אוֹכִיחֶךָ</p>
<p>O Israel, I will testify ¹against you;</p>	<p>וְעוֹלֹתֶיךָ לִנְגִדֵי תָמִיד : ⁹</p>
<p>I am God, ^byour God.</p>	<p>לֹא-אֶקַח מִבֵּיתֶךָ פֶּרֶךְ</p>
<p></p>	<p>מִמְכַלְאֲתֶיךָ עֵתוּדִים : ¹⁰</p>

8 "I do ^anot reprove you for your sacrifices,

And your burnt offerings are continually before Me.

9 "I shall take no ^ayoung bull out of your house

Nor male goats out of your folds.

10 "For ^aevery beast of the forest is Mine,

The cattle on a thousand hills.

11 "I know every ^abird of the mountains,

And everything that moves in the field is ¹Mine.

12 "If I were hungry I would not tell you,

For the ^aworld is Mine, and ¹all it contains.

13 "Shall I eat the flesh of ^{1a}bulls
Or drink the blood of male goats?

14 "Offer to God ^aa sacrifice of thanksgiving

And ^bpay your vows to the Most High;

15 ^aCall upon Me in the day of trouble;

I shall ^brescue you, and you will ^ahonor Me."

Psa. 50:16 But to the wicked God says,

"What right have you to tell of My statutes

And to take ^aMy covenant in your mouth?

כִּי־לִי כָל־חֲתִיתוֹ־יַעַר

בְּהַמְנוֹת בְּהַרְרֵי־אַלְפָּה : 11

יַדְעֹתַי כָּל־עֹף־הָרִים וְזִיו

שְׂוֵי עִמְדָי : 12 אִם־אַרְעֵב

לֹא־אֹמַר לָךְ כִּי־לִי תִבֶלֶת

וּמְלֶאכֶה : 13 הֲאוֹכֵל בֶּשָׂר

אֲבִירִים וְדָם עֲתוּדִים

אֶשְׁתֶּה : 14 זָבַח לֵאלֹהִים

תּוֹדָה וְשִׁלְמִים לְעֹלְיוֹן נְדַרְיָךְ :

15 וְקָרָאתִי בַיּוֹם צָרָה

אֶחֱלֶצֶךָ וְתִכְבְּדֵנִי : 16

וְלֹרְשָׁעִי אֹמַר אֱלֹהִים מַה־

לָךְ לְסַפֵּר תִּקְוִי וְתִשָּׂא בְרִיתִי

עָלַי־כִּיךָ : 17 וְאַתָּה שָׁנֵאתָ

מוֹסֵר וְתִשְׁלַךְ דְּבַר־י

אֲחֵרְיָךְ : 18 אִם־רָאִיתָ גִּבּוֹר

וְתָרַץ עִמּוֹ וְעַם מְנַאֲפִים

תִּלְקַח : 19 כִּיךָ שִׁלַּחַתָּ

בְּרַעַה וְלִשְׁוֹנֶךָ תִּצְמִיד

מִרְמָה : 20 תִּשָּׁב בְּאֶתְיָךְ

תִּדְבֹר בְּבֶן־אִמְךָ תִּתֵּן־דָּבָר :

21 אֵלֶּה עֲשִׂיתָ וְהִתְחַלֵּשְׁתִּי

דְּפִיתָ הַיּוֹת־אֶתֶּיָה כַּמוֹךְ

17 "For you ^ahate discipline,
And you ^bcast My words behind
you.

18 "When you see a thief, you ^{1a}are
pleased with him,
And ²you ^bassociate with
adulterers.

19 "You ^{1a}let your mouth loose in
evil
And your ^btongue frames deceit.

20 "You sit and ^aspeak against your
brother;
You slander your own mother's
son.

21 "These things you have done and
^aI kept silence;
You thought that I was just like
you;
I will ^breprove you and state *the*
case in order before your eyes.

Psa. 50:22 "Now consider this,
you who ^aforget God,
Or I will ^btear *you* in pieces, and
there will be none to deliver.

23 "He who ^aoffers a sacrifice of
thanksgiving honors Me;
And to him who ^{1b}orders *his* way
aright
I shall ^cshow the salvation of
God."

אוֹכִיחֶךָ וְאַעְרֹכָהּ לְעֵינֶיךָ :
22 בִּינֹנָא זֹאת שִׁכְחִי אֱלֹהִים
פֶּן־אֶשְׂרֹף וְאֵין מִצִּיל : 23
זִבַּח תּוֹדָה יִכְבְּדֵנִי וְשֵׁם
דְּרֹךְ אֲרָאֵנוּ בִּישַׁע אֱלֹהִים :

References Psalm 50:0

¹Chr 15:17; 2 Chr 29:30

Psalm 50:1

^aJosh 22:22

^bPs 113:3

Psalm 50:2

^aPs 48:2; Lam 2:15

^bDeut 33:2; Ps 80:1; 94:1

Psalm 50:3

^aPs 96:13

^bLev 10:2; Num 16:35; Ps 97:3; Dan 7:10

^cPs 18:12, 13

Psalm 50:4

^aDeut 4:26; 31:28; 32:1; Is 1:2

Psalm 50:5

^aPs 30:4; 37:28; 52:9

^bEx 24:7; 2 Chr 6:11; Ps 25:10

^cPs 50:8

Psalm 50:6

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 89:5; 97:6

^bPs 75:7; 96:13

Psalm 50:7

¹Or *to*

^aPs 49:1; 81:8

^bEx 20:2; Ps 48:14

Psalm 50:8

^aPs 40:6; 51:16; Is 1:11; Hos 6:6

Psalm 50:9

^aPs 69:31

Psalm 50:10

^aPs 104:24

Psalm 50:11

¹Or *in My mind*; lit *with Me*

^aMatt 6:26

Psalm 50:12

¹Lit *its fullness*

^aEx 19:5; Deut 10:14; Ps 24:1; 1 Cor 10:26

Psalm 50:13

¹Lit *strong ones*

^aPs 50:9

Psalm 50:14

^aPs 27:6; 69:30; 107:22; 116:17; Hos 14:2; Rom 12:1; Heb 13:15

^bNum 30:2; Deut 23:21; Ps 22:25; 56:12; 61:8; 65:1; 76:11

Psalm 50:15

^aPs 91:15; 107:6, 13; Zech 13:9

^bPs 81:7

^cPs 22:23

Psalm 50:16

^aIs 29:13

Psalm 50:17

^aProv 5:12; 12:1; Rom 2:21, 22

^b1 Kin 14:9; Neh 9:26

Psalm 50:18

¹Some ancient versions read *run together*

²Lit *your part is with*

^aRom 1:32

^b1 Tim 5:22

Psalm 50:19

¹Lit *send*

^aPs 10:7

^bPs 36:3; 52:2

Psalm 50:20

^aJob 19:18; Matt 10:21

Psalm 50:21

^aEcc1 8:11; Is 42:14; 57:11

^bPs 90:8

Psalm 50:22

^aJob 8:13; Ps 9:17

^bPs 7:2

Psalm 50:23

¹Lit *sets*

^aPs 50:14

^bPs 85:13

^cPs 91:16

Targum

Psa. 50:1 A hymn composed by Asaph. Mighty is God; the LORD spoke at the Creation a song; and he carved out the earth from the rising of the sun to its setting. ² The perfection and the beginning of the eternal creation is from Zion; and from there its beauty is complete, God will be revealed. ³ The righteous will say on the great day of judgment, "Our God will come, and he will not neglect to vindicate his people"; fire will blaze before him, and around him a storm will rage mightily. ⁴ He will call to the angels of the height above, and to the righteous of the earth below, to extend judgment to his people. ⁵ Gather to me, my pious ones, who have made my covenant, and fulfilled my Torah, and have engaged in prayer, which is likened to a sacrifice. ⁶

And the angels of the height will recount his righteousness, for God is the judge forever. ⁷ Hear, O my people, and I will speak, O Israel; and I will testify to you; I am God, your God. ⁸ I am not rebuking you on account of your sacrifices that you did not offer before me in exile, for your holocausts that your fathers offered are in front of me always. ⁹ From the day that my sanctuary was laid waste, I have not accepted a bull from your hands, or rams from your flock. ¹⁰ For mine are all the animals of the forest, and I have prepared for the righteous in the Garden of Eden clean beasts and a wild bull who grazes every day on a thousand mountains. ¹¹ Manifest before me are all the kinds of birds who fly in the air of heaven; and the rooster whose legs rest on the earth, while his head reaches to heaven, rejoicing before me. ¹² If the time of the continual morning sacrifice should arrive, I would not tell you; for mine is the earth and its fullness. ¹³ From the day my sanctuary was laid waste, I have not accepted the flesh of the sacrifice of fatlings, and the priests have not sprinkled the blood of rams before me. ¹⁴ Subdue the evil impulse and it will be reckoned before the LORD as a sacrifice of thanksgiving; and pay to the Most High your vows. ¹⁵ And pray in my presence in the day of trouble; I will save you, for you will glorify me. ¹⁶ But to the

wicked who has not repented, and prays in impiety, the LORD says, "Why do you recite my covenant, and swear by my name, and invoke my covenant with your mouth?" ¹⁷ But you hate the rebuke of the wise, and you have cast my words behind you. ¹⁸ If you saw a thief, you ran after him; and you have placed your portion with adulterers. ¹⁹ You have loosened your mouth to utter evil speech ; and your tongue adheres to speaking deceit. ²⁰ You will sit with your brother, you will speak lies against your mother's son, you will cast aspersions. ²¹ These bad deeds you did and I waited for you to repent; you thought you would be at peace forever; you said in your heart, "I will be strong like you"; I will rebuke you in this world, and I will prepare the judgment of Gehenna before you in the world to come. ²² Now understand this, you wicked who have forgotten God, lest I break your might, with no one to save. ²³ He who sacrifices the evil impulse, it will be reckoned to him like a sacrifice of thanksgiving, and he honors me; and whoever will remove the evil way, I will show him the redemption of the LORD.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm describes the intense desire of the LORD to reveal Himself to his beloved Israel. However, the LORD will not make His presence known to His children until they desire it. One has to demonstrate a sincere desire to draw near him. The Psalmist indicates an effective means of drawing close to the LORD. This is accomplished by studying the meaning of the Torah. It is not enough to simply read the Torah. One has to learn the many levels of understanding in each passage. Rabbi Chiam of Volozhin said that Torah study makes a person worthy of being the LORD's son.

Superscript and verse one

יְיָ (el) – means "God." The common usage of this word is to emphasize God as the "mighty God." This word's connotation is that the Psalmist refers to the strength of the LORD, which enables life, breathing, growth, and our ability to know the LORD.

A psalm of Asaf. The mighty God of Israel has spoken and calls forth from the earth from sunrise to sunset.

Verse two

Mount Zion became the place where the Word of the LORD given to Israel at Mount Sinai would reside during King David's time. It is on the Temple mount in Jerusalem, on Mount Zion, where Solomon built the LORD's house on earth. Ancient Israelites

believed that the LORD's perfection and beauty always shined from the mountain. Zion is considered sacred today and will always be sacred.

Out of Zion, the epitome of beauty, the LORD has already appeared.

Verse three

The LORD reveals Himself utilizing His word. Israel sensed the presence of the LORD for the first time at Mount Sinai when Moses came down from the mountain with the two tablets of the LORD's word. That feeling will come to the people if they study the Torah.

The LORD will return and will not be silent; a fire devours before Him, and it is exceedingly stormy around Him.

Verse four

The LORD appointed the heaven and earth to be guarantors and witnesses to Israel's fulfillment of their promise to the LORD. The Ten Commandments is a treaty between the LORD and Israel. The LORD says that He will protect Israel. In turn, Israel agreed to live by the LORD's commandments. Now the LORD calls upon heaven and earth to be His witnesses and to proclaim His judgment over His people.

He calls to the heavens and the earth to judge His people.

Verse five

אָסַף (es'foo) – means “gather” and it is in possessive form. This word denotes a gathering into one spiritual unit. Judgment is against the entire nation, not individually. People believe they will be individually judged in the Modern and Post-Modern world. Since no one has returned from the dead to tell us the process, this point is hard to debate. However, in this Psalm, the Psalmist says that Israel will be judged as one large spiritual unit and not individually.

Gather as one spiritual unit My devoted persons who uphold My covenant as they perform the rite of sacrifice.

Verse six

And the heavens declare His righteousness, for God Himself is the judge. Meditate upon this verse.

Verse seven

The Psalmist tells us that the LORD has something to say to His people. This is a serious thing so pay attention. Above all things, the LORD expects His people to worship Him as the guide to one's deeds and as the ruler of one's destiny. “To testify against you "means telling the people what they are doing wrong.”

Hear, O My people, I wish to speak; O Israel I wish to testify against you; I am God, your God.

Verses eight to twelve

The LORD reminds us that He is the ultimate owner of everything.

I do not reprove you for your sacrifices, and your burnt offerings are continually before Me.

I shall take no young bull out of your house nor male goats out of your folds.

For every beast of the forest is Mine, the cattle on a thousand hills.

I know every bird of the mountains, and everything that moves in the field is Mine.

If I were hungry I would not tell you, for the world is Mine, and all it contains.

Verse thirteen

The LORD does not eat meat, nor does He drink blood. The LORD did command Israel to offer sacrifices of flesh and blood. The sacrifices were never to afford the LORD the sensual pleasure of devouring flesh and blood. The flesh symbolized the sacrifice of the strength of your muscles while working within the LORD's laws which brings His favor. The blood signifies the consecration of a person's spirit so that it may strive upwards to the high plane at which it will meet the LORD's favor.

The spiritual awareness of the sacrificial system was first an acknowledgment that the LORD is the creator of all things. It is through the Shekinah that the presence of the LORD is given to those who seek it. Without the Light of the LORD through the Shekinah and the Nukvah of Binah nothing would exist. Raising an animal that can be sacrificed to the LORD required time and resources. The work required to feed and care for the animal would be rewarded by the LORD because sacrificing the animal shows trust in the LORD and that one does not expect anything special from

the LORD. It is a mitzvah to sacrifice something to the LORD without any expectations. The LORD does reward His people who make the sacrifice without strings attached nor expecting something in return.

Ancient people believed that one's spirit was in one's blood. Therefore, the blood sacrifice symbolizes giving one's spirit to live following the Torah. It was a reminder that one must place complete trust and faith in the LORD. By following the Torah, a person proves their covenant.

But do I eat the flesh of bulls or drink the blood of goats?

Verse fourteen

The Psalmist reminds us that it is important to acknowledge the gifts from the LORD daily.

Offer an acknowledgment to God and give your vows to the Most High.

Verse fifteen

Turn to the LORD in times of trouble. The covenant between the LORD and His people will renew with every offering.

Call upon Me in times of trouble, says the LORD; I will make you free, and you will honor me.

Verse sixteen

Wicked people are those who know the statutes of the LORD and have decided to ignore them. The LORD demands to know why some people think it is okay to do this.

To the wicked, God says, What right have you to violate my statutes and to speak about my covenant?

Verse seventeen

Every word in the Torah has explicit implications upon our desires and ambitions, speech and actions, and thus banishes sin from our midst.

For you hate discipline, and you cast my words behind you.

Verse eighteen

The LORD tells the people that some are not thieves or adulterers; however, they approve of them because they allow them to circumvent the law. Today this is equivalent to major US city District Attorneys not prosecuting criminals. In 2022 one can shoplift \$950 of merchandise in California and not go to jail. The leaders of California may not be criminals. Still, since they allow criminal activities to go unpunished, the LORD says they are guilty.

When you see a thief, you are pleased with him and associate with adulterers.

Verses nineteen & twenty

These verses are directed at the wicked people of the world. The LORD accuses them of expounding the Torah, but they use deceit and slander when committing their crimes.

You have let loose your mouth for evil, and your tongue frames deceit.

If you sit, you speak against your brother; you slander your own mother's son.

Verse twenty-one

The LORD said that since lawless acts had gone unpunished, the people must have thought that the LORD agreed. The LORD wants lawless people punished for their actions. It is wrong for devout people to allow the wicked to continue in their ways.

These things you have done and I have kept silent; therefore, you thought that, in fact, I was like yourself. Consequently, I reprove you and set it before your eyes.

Verse twenty-two

The LORD offers the wicked an opportunity to return to Him.

Now understand this, you who have forgotten God, lest I could tear in pieces and there is none to deliver.

Verse twenty-three

Salvation is found in the LORD.

He who offers acknowledgment honors Me in truth, and to him who bases his way of life thereon, I shall show the salvation of God.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A psalm of Asaf. The mighty God of Israel has spoken and calls forth from the earth from sunrise to sunset.

Out of Zion, the epitome of beauty, the LORD has already appeared.

The LORD will return and will not be silent; a fire devours before Him, and it is exceedingly stormy around Him.

He calls to the heavens and the earth to judge His people.

Gather as one spiritual unit My devoted persons who uphold My covenant as they perform the rite of sacrifice.

And the heavens declare His righteousness, for God Himself is the judge. Meditate upon this verse.

Hear, O My people, I wish to speak; O Israel I wish to testify against you; I am God, your God.

I do not reprove you for your sacrifices, and your burnt offerings are continually before Me.

I shall take no young bull out of your house nor male goats out of your folds.

For every beast of the forest is Mine, the cattle on a thousand hills.

I know every bird of the mountains, and everything that moves in the field is Mine.

If I were hungry I would not tell you, for the world is Mine, and all it contains.

But do I eat the flesh of bulls or drink the blood of goats?

Offer an acknowledgment to God and give your vows to the Most High.

Call upon Me in times of trouble, says the LORD; I will make you free, and you will honor me.

To the wicked, God says, What right have you to violate my statutes and to speak about my covenant?

For you hate discipline, and you cast my words behind you.

When you see a thief, you are pleased with him and associate with adulterers.

You have let loose your mouth for evil, and your tongue frames deceit.

If you sit, you speak against your brother; you slander your own mother's son.

These things you have done and I have kept silent; therefore, you thought that, in fact, I was like yourself. Consequently, I reprove you and set it before your eyes.

Now understand this, you who have forgotten God, lest I could tear in pieces and there is none to deliver.

He who offers acknowledgment honors Me in truth, and to him who bases his way of life thereon, I shall show the salvation of God.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

